

DYNAMIC FAILURE ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES AND CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

Alexander E. Bogdanovich
Latvian Academy of Sciences
Engineering and Technology Center
Riga, Latvia , U.S.S.R.

ABSTRACT

The problem of theoretical prediction of initial failure and ply-by-ply failure processes in laminated composite rectangular plates and cylindrical shells under various kinds of dynamical loading is under consideration. Methods of calculation of a "history of deformation" are presented. The phenomenological failure criteria are used to predict the lower bound of "critical" parameters of a dynamic load, corresponding to the start of failure in a structural element. A ply-by-ply failure model and calculation algorithm are described. By use of them, the second, higher bound of "critical" parameters of a dynamic load, corresponding to the total exhaustion of a load-bearing capacity of a structural element is calculated. The application of a general procedure is illustrated on the examples of failure analysis for a thin-walled imperfect laminated graphite/epoxy cylindrical shells under short-time impulses of axial compression or external pressure and for a graphite/epoxy plates under low-velocity transverse impact.

KEY WORDS: Thick laminate, low velocity impact, dynamic response, failure.

1. INTRODUCTION

The necessity of solving the problems of deformation and failure for composite shells and plates operating in combined static and dynamic regimes, can be ascribed to the constantly increasing use of these elements in primary structures. The full-scale dynamic and long-term tests are very complex and expensive, therefore the problem of theoretical prediction of structural integrity, durability and reliability becomes more and more actual. In view of very complicated nature of transient processes in laminated anisotropic structural elements, one of the main objectives is uncovering the physical essence of phenomena, occurring both in material (the material response) and in a structure (the structural response) under specified type of loading condition. The first depends on "local", structural parameters (mechanical properties of fibers, matrix, interfaces, as long as reinforcement angles, thicknesses of plies, their sequence and total number in a laminate). The second depends on "global" parameters (stiffness characteristics of a laminate, geometrical characteristics of a structure, imperfections of a various nature, specified boundary conditions, interaction between a structure and external loads, preliminary loading,

environmental effects).

Some aspects of the general problem were considered in a monograph [1], devoted to dynamics of laminated composite cylindrical shells. It is worth to underline, that for actual shells and plates, having initial imperfections (even very small ones), and operating under real loading conditions, it is practically impossible to separate such a classical problems as deformation, stability, buckling and failure. A comparatively slow growth of deformations during the initial stage of compressive loading, a subsequent abrupt transition of this process into intensive nonaxisymmetric buckling, and the following development of the local inelastic deformations or zones of local damages in the material, represent different sides of a joint complex process. We can find out only, what is the dominating feature of this process in a prescribed situation. This conclusion is based on a number of particular problems, solved in [1] for various laminated orthotropic thin-walled cylindrical shells (nonlinear parametrical vibrations, short-time impulsive loading of a shell by axisymmetric longitudinal compression, external pressure, their mutual combination or combinations with static loads of the same type). In the paper the problem of theoretical prediction of the initial failure and ply-by-ply failure in laminated composite cylindrical shells and rectangular plates is under consideration.

2. PLY-BY-PLY FAILURE MODEL

Cylindrical shell is loaded by a short-time axisymmetric impulsive longitudinal compression or uniformly distributed external pressure, rectangular plate - by transversal impact applied to the upper face surface. The first problem is to calculate the "history of deformation" during the event of loading: to determine deformation vector components, stress and strain tensors components versus time in the whole volume of a shell or plate. This goal is achieved for a cylindrical shell on the basis of the geometrically nonlinear theory of thin orthotropic elastic shells by use of variational or finite - difference methods[1]. Special procedures were elaborated to calculate transverse stresses [1] as to evaluate the danger of interlaminar or transversal intralaminar failure. For a thick rectangular plate under short -time impulse or low-velocity impact loading, the analysis is based on the equations of three-dimensional theory of elasticity for laminated orthotropic media. Special numerical procedure was elaborated to calculate stress-strain state in a plate [2,3]. It is based on the spline approximation of displacements, and makes it possible to obtain practically continuous distributions of transverse stress components through the thickness of a laminate, even in the case of sharply varying transversal elastic characteristics in adjacent layers.

The second problem is to determine the load (impulse) value and, correspondingly, the time instant value, at which for specified strength characteristics of a composite monolayer, at least in one point of a shell (plate) the prescribed failure criterion is satisfied. As the result, the first ultimate magnitude of a load (impulse) has to be found, the mode of initial failure has to be identified, and the location of initial failure zone has to be assessed. This procedure was realized for a laminated cylindrical shell by use of the quadratic version of a tensor-polynomial strength criterion, together with additional control of failure mode by use of the maximum stress criterion [1]. For a laminated plate, the maximum stress criterion has to be used in this paper. Such an analysis is valuable, if there is presupposed requirement to maintain integrity and hermeticity of walls of the structural element during the whole time of its exploitation. However, in those situations, when there is a requirement to ensure the total load-bearing capacity of the structural element only, without any attention for its state after its function is finished, this approach to the analysis has to be improved.

The solution of the third problem, i. e., calculation of a process of ply-by-ply failure beyond the time instant corresponding to the first failure event, needs to involve in the calculation procedure a model of reduced stiffnesses. Matrix cracking and fiber debonding from the matrix in a layer, as well as "refusal" of a part of fibers due to their breakage or loss of stability, become

admissible. In such a way, taking into consideration that each failure event occurs only in one layer and corresponds to fairly definite mode of failure in the fibrous material, makes it possible to raise the lower bound of an ultimate load (impulse). The final goal of a calculation is to obtain the second bound value of the ultimate load (impulse), corresponding to the time instant value, at which the total exhaustion of a load-bearing capacity of a structure is set up. The general procedure described above allows one to investigate jointly the processes of transient deformation, dynamic buckling and ply-by-ply failure of structural elements made of laminated fibrous composite materials.

The reduction of stiffnesses of a layer and, consequently, stiffnesses of the entire laminate, is needed at those time instants, when, in accordance with the strength criterion used, any of the possible failure modes is being realized in a layer. A number of different stiffness reduction models have been used for predicting of ultimate loads in various static problems. One of the most perfect models was proposed and used for particular problems in [4]. It presupposes that there are seven variants of failure events in a unidirectionally reinforced composite (Table 1). Here, $\sigma_{11}^{*(i)}$ and $\sigma_{22}^{*(i)}$ are dimensionless stresses along and across fiber direction, related to respective material strength characteristics (in tension and compression, correspondingly); $\sigma_{12}^{*(i)}$ is in-plane shear stress related to the shear strength magnitude; $E_1^{(i)}$ and $E_2^{(i)}$ are elastic moduli of a layer along and across fiber direction, correspondingly; $G_{12}^{(i)}$ is in-plane shear modulus. Also $E_1^0(i)$, $E_2^0(i)$, $G_{12}^0(i)$ are the moduli of a layer at the initial state. In addition to the model [4], we use here also some information on nonlinear shear behaviour of a unidirectionally reinforced layer for variants 5 and 7 in Table 1: $G_{12}^{(i)c}$ is the current shear modulus which can be found from the experimental $\sigma_{12} - \epsilon_{12}$ curve for a monolayer.

The algorithm for the analysis consists in the following. Let us assume that at the time instant $\tau = \tau^* = \tau_1^{(i)}$, in a certain point of the i -th ply of a structural element, the event of initial failure takes place. At this time instant, the $\sigma_{11}^{*(i)}$, $\sigma_{22}^{*(i)}$, $\sigma_{12}^{*(i)}$ values are calculated, and all the seven conditions of the Table 1 are checked up. Depending on the variant realized, the magnitudes of a particular membrane C_{kl} stiffnesses and bending D_{kl} stiffnesses are reduced stepwise, having after reduction the values $C_{kl}^{(i)}$, $D_{kl}^{(i)}$. They are inserted into equations of motion of a structural element and, as a result of a solution of the equations at $\tau > \tau_1^{(i)}$, the characteristics of deformation process during this time interval are obtained. Proceeding with this algorithm, one can obtain the sequence of ply failure instants $\tau_1^{(i)}$, $\tau_2^{(i)}$, ..., $\tau_n^{(q)}$, where a superscript indicates the layer in which this failure event occurred, and a subscript indicates the number of a failure event. The latter of these events, corresponding to the time instant $\tau_n^{(q)}$, is determined in accordance with the condition of a zero value, at least for one of the stiffnesses C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{66} of a package as a whole. The algorithm proposed allows also to assess the sequence of failure events in a package and to obtain step-wise continuous dependencies of stress-strain state characteristics on time.

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES FOR A CYLINDRICAL SHELL

The following numerical examples illustrate application of the algorithm for laminated graphite-epoxy cylindrical shells having specified field of nonaxisymmetric initial geometrical imperfections, under the effect of axisymmetric impulse of axial compression $P(\tau)$ or the effect of uniformly distributed impulse of external pressure $q(\tau)$, Fig.1. The influence of duration and shape of these impulses is of a special interest.

The results obtained for a four-ply and eight-ply shells are presented in Table 2. Here, $\tau_k^{(j)}$ is the time instant of the k -th failure event in the j -th layer; x^* and y^* are the coordinates of

the k-th failure site. As it can be seen, for both packages the exhaustion of a load-bearing capacity of a shell is due to the condition $C_{22}=0$ being fulfilled. For the loading program b), there are no failures assessed in a shell, whereas for intermediate loading programs between a) and b), with $P(\tau)$ changing within the time interval $70 < \tau < 140$, both the effects fulfilments of the condition $C_{22}=0$ as well as diverse failure modes in a part of shell layers are assessed. It should be noted also that a time interval between the first and the last failure events is rather short, compared to the time interval prior to the first ply failure. This is associated with an abrupt growth of stress-strain state characteristics during comparatively short time interval, when longitudinal impulse is applied.

The results for the case of external pressure illustrate the effect of increase of ply number in a package. The initial and subsequent failure events were calculated for a shell having four and eight layers (Table 3). Although from the viewpoint of membrane and flexural stiffnesses, all these packages are identical, the process of ply-by-ply failure is prolonged in time essentially upon the division of a monolayer through its thickness into several sublayers, having identical elastic characteristics. In all the cases, as it is seen from Table 3, only two variants of failure (number 3 and 7 from Table 1) are being realized. The load-bearing capacity exhaustion is the result of fulfilment of the condition $C_{22}=0$.

From the numerical results obtained, it follows also that for all external pressure impulse shapes (see Fig. 1), there occur only failures of types 3 and 7. The fact also should be emphasized that both the main characteristics of the process -sequence of ply failures and failure modes realized in each layer, as well as the coordinates of failure sites, do not depend practically on the shape of an impulse applied. Also, at all loading programs the load-bearing capacity exhaustion occurs as a result of fulfilment of the condition $C_{22}=0$. Numerical examples illustrate also the existence of such loading impulses, the effect of which is inadmissible, from the viewpoint of the initial failure criterion, though they do not lead to failure over the entire wall thickness of a multilayer structural element.

The described algorithm for analyzing ply-by-ply failure processes does not take into account that the character of failure initiation is local due to strictly localized sites of intensive dynamical buckling [1]. Therefore, the obtained time interval up to the complete exhaustion of a load bearing capacity, will be eventually underrated. The improved algorithms are needed to take into account local effects. In order to develop such an algorithms, it is necessary to work out special models to account generation, growth and accumulation of local damages both in a layer and from layer to layer.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES FOR A RECTANGULAR PLATE

The following numerical example illustrates applicability of the procedure of theoretical prediction of the location and size of impact damage zones in a laminated graphite/epoxy plate. The problem is treated in a two - dimensional approach (cylindrical bending). The results were obtained for a case of fixed 2.5 J impact energy at several combinations of mass and velocity of impactor.

The plate under consideration is assembled of a unidirectionally reinforced graphite/epoxy monolayers (fiber GY 70) having following elastic characteristics:

$$E_1=102.1 \text{ GPa}, E_2=6.96 \text{ GPa}, G_{12}=4.16 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{12}=0.318, \rho=1630 \text{ kg/m}^3.$$

The geometrical parameters are: length $L=0.2$ m, thickness $H=0.01$ m. All the layers in a package are of equal thickness. Ply layup is $[0^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ]$ (fibers in the upper layer are oriented in x-direction).

Let us designate R_1^\pm, R_2^\pm, R_τ the ultimate strength values for a unidirectionally reinforced monolayer in the direction of fibers, in the transverse direction and in shear, accordingly. The sign

“+” corresponds to tension, “-” to compression. If any stress component at some point inside a plate reaches its ultimate value, the point is marked at the two-dimensional map of impact damages (x, z -section of a plate). In Fig.2 it is shown the left half of such a map; rigid body impact takes place in the center of a plate ($x=0.5$ section). The damage zone corresponding to the condition $\sigma_{11} \geq R_1^+$ is marked by dots, the damage zone corresponding to the condition $\sigma_{22} \leq -R_2^-$ is marked by black paint, the damage zone corresponding to $\sigma_{22} \geq R_2^+$ condition is marked by vertical shade, and the damage zone corresponding to $\sigma_{12} \leq R_\tau$ condition is marked by oblique shade.

By using the maximum stress criterion (as well as any other phenomenological strength criteria), one can determine in principle only one, the very first point on the map of damages. After each of the failure events we have to reduce certain local stiffness characteristics in a lamina and, correspondingly, in a laminate as a whole. We have also to take into account a local overstress in the vicinity of each damage appeared. Such an analysis needs special procedures. The results shown in Fig.2 were obtained without taking into account these effects. They can illustrate, therefore, only some general features in the development of impact damages and their final extent. From these results we can evaluate also intersections of damage zones corresponding to different modes of failure. The “final” maps of impact damage zones presented in Fig.2, contain the largest damage zone for each mode of failure during the whole impact event at the prescribed combination of a mass and velocity of impactor. The following strength characteristics were used: $R_1^+ = 230$ MPa, $R_2^+ = 20.7$ MPa, $R_2^- = 186$ MPa, $R_\tau = 59.3$ MPa. The time instants pointed out in Fig.2, correspond to the largest size of each damage zone during the whole period of impact interaction.

It can be noted from the results, that for heavy impactors the dominating mode of failure is fiber breakage on the bottom surface. At $M=25$ g, there is a zone of internal transversal shear cracks (rather small at $V_0=13.5$ m/sec and much more extended, going through all the plies at $V_0=27$ m/sec). In the case of $M=1$ g and $V_0=70$ m/sec, there are two partly intersecting zones of transversal shear and normal tension cracks. In such a situation, the phenomenon well known for metal plates, namely spalling failure can be expected. Let us note also that at $V_0=27$ m/sec (Fig.2,c,d,e) there is a small zone in the vicinity of impactor where magnitude of transversal normal stress exceeds the R_2^- ultimate value. Therefore, starting from this value of impact velocity, it is necessary to take into account local inelastic behaviour of a composite in the vicinity of impactor.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Laminated composite structural elements are very sensitive to short-time impulses and low velocity impacts, that are very probable during the technological cycle or service time. Various types of internal invisible or barely visible damages can be predicted by using the models and methods of computer aided analysis described in the paper. It is important to underline the reasonable effects of impulse duration and amplitude, impact velocity, mass of impactor, number of layers and their layout in a laminate on the dominating mode of failure, size of damage zones and time interval up to the first ply failure and up to the total exhaustion of a load bearing capacity of a specified composite part. Incorporating in the general prediction of durability, the analysis of behaviour of composite components during rather short intervals of influence of expected technological and service dynamic loads, one can obtain more realistic results on the life time and reliability of the structure.

6. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Programs of impulse loading by axial compression (a, b) and external pressure (c-j).

Figure 2 . Calculated impact damage zones for $M=17 \text{ kg}, V_0=0.48 \text{ m/sec}$ (a), $M=25 \text{ g}, V_0=13.5 \text{ m/sec}$ (b), $M=3 \text{ g}, V_0=40.5 \text{ m/sec}$ (c), $M=1 \text{ g}, V_0=70 \text{ m/sec}$ (d), $M=25 \text{ g}, V_0=27 \text{ m/sec}$ (e).

TABLE 1 The scheme of reduction of stiffness characteristics of a unidirectionally reinforced monolayer

The number of variant	Failure mode	$E_1^{(i)}$	$E_2^{(i)}$	$G_{12}^{(i)}$
1	$\sigma^{*(i)}_{11} \geq 1$	0	0	0
2	$\sigma^{*(i)}_{11} \leq -1; \sigma^{*(i)}_{22} \geq 0$	0	0	0
3	$\sigma^{*(i)}_{11} \leq -1; \sigma^{*(i)}_{22} < 0$	0	$E_2^{0(i)}$	0
4	$\sigma^{*(i)}_{22} \geq 1$	$E_1^{0(i)}$	0	0
5	$\sigma^{*(i)}_{22} \leq -1$	$E_1^{0(i)}$	0	$\tilde{G}_{12}^{(i)}$
6	$\sigma^{*(i)}_{12} \geq 1; \sigma^{*(i)}_{22} \geq 0$	$E_1^{0(i)}$	0	0
7	$\sigma^{*(i)}_{12} \geq 1; \sigma^{*(i)}_{22} < 0$	$E_1^{0(i)}$	$E_2^{0(i)}$	$\tilde{G}_{12}^{(i)}$

TABLE 2 Characteristics of ply-by-ply failure process under axial dynamic compression (loading program a)

The number of failure event, k	$\tau_k^{(j)}$	The number of layer, j	Failure mode	x^*/L	y^*/R
$[0/90^\circ]_s$					
1	85,50	4	3	0,96	3,14
2	88,01	4	5	0,96	0
3	88,26	1	6	0,96	3,14
4; 5	88,27	3; 2	4	0,96	0
$[0/90/0/90^\circ]_s$					
1	79,75	8	3	0,96	3,14
2	80,00	6	3	1,10	0
3	80,26	8	5	0,96	0
4	80,27	1	6	0,96	0
5	80,52	3	6	0,96	2,40
6	80,53	6	5	0,96	2,40
7; 8; 9;	80,54	2; 4; 5	4	0,96	0

TABLE 3 Characteristics of ply-by-ply failure process under external dynamic pressure
(loading program c)

The number of failure event, k	$\tau_k^{(j)}$	The number of layer, j	Failure mode	x^*/L	y^*/R
1	2	3	4	5	6
[90/0°] _s					
1	26,10	3	3	0,92	3,14
2	26,65	2	3	0,96	2,72
3	26,66	4	3	0,84	3,14
4	27,20	4	7	0,90	3,14
5	27,80	1	3	0,92	2,72
[90/90/0/0°] _s					
1	26,10	6	3	0,92	3,14
2	26,65	3	3	0,96	2,72
3	26,66	8	3	0,84	3,14
4	26,81	5	3	0,94	3,14
5	27,01	7	3	0,84	3,14
6	27,21	8	7	0,90	3,14
7	27,56	4	3	0,98	2,72
8	27,71	1	7	0,92	2,72
9	27,96	7	7	0,90	3,14
10	28,61	2	1	0,94	2,72
[90/90/90/90/0/0/0/0°] _s					
1	26,10	12	3	0,92	3,14
2	26,40	11	3	0,92	3,14
3	26,65	5	3	0,96	2,72
4	26,66	16	3	0,82	3,14
5: 6	26,81	10; 15	3	0,94	3,14
7	27,01	6	3	0,96	2,72
8	27,02	14	3	0,84	3,14
9: 10	27,21	13; 16	3	0,84	3,14
11	27,26	9	3	0,96	3,14
12	27,52	7	3	0,98	2,72
13	27,57	15	7	0,90	3,14
14	27,72	1	7	0,92	2,72
15	27,92	14	7	0,90	3,14
16	28,12	2	7	0,92	2,72
17	28,37	13	7	0,90	3,14
18	28,72	8	3	0,98	2,09
19	28,78	3	7	0,94	2,72
20	29,43	4	7	0,96	2,72

